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Abstract	This deliverable presents the final state of three key technical components within AD4GD: the final architecture of the Dataspace deployment, the data catalogue and metadata and the data trustworthiness framework.
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ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Definition
API	Application Programming Interface
AWS	Amazon Web Services
CAMS	Copernicus Atmosphere Monitoring
CKAN	Comprehensive Knowledge Archive Network
CRW	Centroid Reflection Wavelength
CSV	Comma-Separated Values
CSW	Catalogue Service for the Web
DAPS	Dynamic Attribute Provisioning Service
DAT	Dynamic Attribute Token
DCAT	Data Catalogue Vocabulary
DCP	Decentralized Claims Protocol
DS	DataSpace
DSP	DataSpace Protocol
DSSC	Data Spaces Support Centre
DSSC	Data Spaces Support Centre
DTF	Data Trustworthiness Framework
EDC	Eclipse Dataspace Connectors
EEA	European Environment Agency
ERA5	The fifth generation ECMWF atmospheric reanalysis of the global climate covering the period from January 1940 to present
FACTS	Federated Agile Collaborative Trusted System
FC	Federated Catalogue
FROST	Fraunhofer Opensource SensorThings-Server
GDDS	Green Deal Data Space
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GeoDCAT	Geospatial Data Catalogue Vocabulary
GIS	Geographic Information System
HPC	High Performance Computing
HTML	Hypertext Markup Language
HTTP	Hyper Text Transfer Protocol
IAM	Identity Access Management
IDSA	International Data Spaces Association
INSPIRE	Infrastructure for Spatial Information in Europe

IoT	Internet of Things
IPT	Integrity, Provenance, and Trust
IQR	Interquartile Range
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
JSON-LD	JavaScript Object Notation for Linked Data
MAE	Mean Absolute Error
MSE	Mean Squared Error
MVD	Minimum Viable Dataspace
OGC	Open Geospatial Consortium
OPTICS (Algorithm)	Ordering points to identify the clustering structure (Algorithm)
PM10	Particulate Matter with particles less than 10 micrometres in diameter.
PM2.5	Particulate Matter with particles less than 2.5 micrometres in diameter.
QualityML	Quality Markup Language
RAM	Reference Architecture Model
RDF	Resource Description Framework
REST	Representational State Transfer
RMSE	Root Mean Squared Error
SOSA	Sensor, Observation, Sample, and Actuator
SPI	Service Provider Interface
SSIM	Structural Similarity Index Model
STA	Sensor Things API
STAC	SpatioTemporal Asset Catalogues
STApplus	Sensor Things API plus (extension of STA)
TAPIS	Tables from APIs
TRL	Technical Readiness Level
UI	User Interface
UncertML	Uncertainty Markup Language
URI	Universal Resource Identifier
URL	Universal Resource Locator
WCS	Web Coverage Service
WFS	Web Feature Service
WMS	Web Map Service
XML	Extensible Markup Language

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document presents the final form of the work done in WP 4 and previously partially presented in D4.1 and D4.2, the Dataspace architecture, the data catalogue and metadata system and the data trustworthiness framework. Like in D4.2, the text follows the components' architecture defined by D6.1, focussing primarily on new work done since D4.2:

1. Component 2 – Evaluation of Connector Solutions and Deployments
2. Component 9 – Data catalogue and Metadata
3. Component 11 – Data Trustworthiness Framework

In terms of tasks, this deliverable predominantly discusses work in WP4 “Satellite and Green Deal Data Space Integration”, including tasks 4.2 “Green Deal Data Space Implementation”, 4.3 “Green Data Space integration with third-party services” and 4.4 “Ground truthing and data trustworthiness framework”. It also has overlap with and incorporates work from the three pilot projects within WP6 and the machine learning work being done in WP5.

Section 1: *AD4GD Data Connector deployment for Data Spaces*, details the evolution of the AD4GD data connector features following the data connector validation process achieved during the first half of AD4GD and described in D4.2 It presents the implementation of the project's Data Space node to expose and share some of its main results. This deployment aims to assess and demonstrate the capabilities of the data connector approach to building the Green Deal Data Space, in accordance with IDSA requirements, while providing an example on how to deploy an open-source Dataspace node for other upcoming EC, partner and/or company initiatives. In the final version of the deployment, the FAIRiCUBE and AD4GD has participated in the creation of a single Dataspace going beyond what was foreseen in the DoA of this project.

Section 2: *Data and Metadata Catalogue*, describes the final AD4GD data and metadata catalogue implementation within GeoNetwork, including practices for documenting ISO 19115-compliant metadata, and the methods used to connect the catalogue with other technical components in the Dataspace. It discusses the technologies selected and implemented in AD4GD to support data and metadata cataloguing. The presented solution provides access to internal users via a cloud based MinIO repository for data storage (and for connector deployment for data sharing) and implements a GeoNetwork ISO19115 metadata catalogue (serving as the master copy and the most comprehensive and detailed metadata in AD4GD) that connects with Data Catalogue Vocabulary (DCAT) metadata that is exposed to the rest of the Dataspace using the Eclipse Dataspace Connectors (EDC) Federated catalogue in compliance with IDSA Dataspace Protocol.

Section 3: *Data Trustworthiness Framework*, presents practical examples from the pilots of the application of the framework as defined in D4.2. These include: an assessment of the reliability of citizen science derived water quality data as part of pilot 1, novel intercomparisons between machine learning derived biodiversity connectivity measures and traditional approaches as part of pilot 2, and new IoT air quality sensor correction models presented as part of pilot 3. In addition, section 3.1, presents an exploratory, alternative Dataspace approach called FACTS that is based on an immutable data catalogue developed within the AD4GD project.

1 AD4GD DATA CONNECTOR DEPLOYMENT FOR DATA SPACES

As already pointed in D4.2, the **International Data Spaces Association (IDSA)**¹, presents data connectors as the way to efficiently combine and share heterogeneous data sources through a common interface. Federations of these data connectors create what ultimately defines a Data Space.

During the first half of AD4GD, the project worked on implementing a first version of an IDSA compliant data connector, relying on the Eclipse Data Components software framework. D4.2 evaluated two instances of this first version of the connector by performing a simple data transaction between the provider connector instance and the consumer.

According to Figure 1, the D4.2 scenario implemented a **Provider** Data Connector instance (hosted in the AD4GD cluster and managed by ATOS) to define and store the asset to expose, and a **Consumer** Data Connector instance (hosted in PSNC premises) to execute a transaction and retrieve the exposed asset. The executed steps that validated the interfaces deployed and the connectors' performance were:

1. **Asset definition:** using the management API, a new asset/entity is created for the selected HTTP native data source. This asset includes the endpoint of the original source and the parameters needed to access and retrieve the JSON file object of the test.
2. **Offer creation:** using the management API, the corresponding access restrictions and conditions (policies) are defined and, by creating the corresponding contract, the asset and the policy are linked and exposed as an offer in the Provider's catalogue.
3. **Reading the Provider Catalogue:** using the Consumer API, the Consumer can read the Provider catalogue and select the exposed offer. Previously, both instances of the connector have registered with a common Identity Management service to identify and authenticate the requests between them. For the final implementation, this simple authentication mechanism has evolved to implement the Dynamic Attribute Provisioning Service (DAPS) necessary for the federation and secure communication of the connectors.
4. **Negotiation:** once selected, the consumer connector starts the negotiation process to fulfil and check the corresponding policy and obtain the credentials to transfer the file included in the offer.
5. **File Transfer:** after checking the credentials presented by the consumer, the provider connector allows the transfer. This is done through an HTTP pull request which the provider connector validated and connected to the HTTP Data source, using the parameters defined on its asset. The transfer is executed and stored in the Consumers' selected sink.

¹ IDSA Data Connector Report 2022 https://internationaldataspaces.org/wp-content/uploads/dlm_uploads/IDSA-Data-Connector-Report-November-2022.pdf

Figure 1: Simple test scenario (from D4.2), including the steps to validate a data transfer (JSON file) between connectors.

This scenario (detailed in D4.2) validated the Connector's implementation based on Eclipse EDC carried out during the first half of AD4GD and enabled the project to design and deploy the AD4GD Dataspace during the second stage.

Taking this as the starting point, this section describes the evolution of the connectors' implementation during the second (and final) stage to support all the required features and build the AD4GD catalogue, whilst also details the assets' definition to support the publication of the selected data sources available within AD4GD. It also covers the federation of several connectors from other related projects to build the prototype of an actual Dataspace.

1.1 AD4GD DATA SPACE COMPONENTS

The deployment in D4.3 builds upon the foundation established in D4.2, expanding the capabilities of the Minimum Viable Dataspace (MVD) to support more advanced interactions between provider and consumer tenants. In this sense, the achievements go in two main directions:

- The creation of a **federated catalogue** component that allows the registration of several related connectors, all of them acting as both: data providers and data consumers, allowing the datasets sharing among these registered partners.
- The creation of specific **adaptors** that allow the definition and registration of different HTTP sources as **EDC Assets**, expanding the catalogue offered by AD4GD

This way, the connector's scenario has been evolved from its simple dataset transaction between a provider and a consumer, towards a federated catalogue, with several connectors' sharing their assets, as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: The federated connectors' scenario.

The deployment of this final scenario required the improvement of the existing connectors' building blocks detailed in D4.2, with the latest updates from the Eclipse Dataspace Components² and including the full authentication/identification capabilities set to enable the secure partners' federation. On this final approach, all connector's nodes work at the same time as assets' provider and consumer. This means that all offers are published in a single point, where all registered nodes can access. Note that FAIRiCUBE and AD4GD has collaborated together in the creation of this single Dataspace

Figure 3 details the final set of components deployed to support the federated scenario and updates the UML diagram of the simple data transfer scenario shown in D4.2. Focused only on the two initial connectors' instances, the system still adheres to a provider-consumer architecture, now enriched with new components and improved features that enhance security and data exchange.

² <https://github.com/eclipse-edc>

Figure 3: Deployment architecture UML diagram

Short overview of the main components:

- **Data dashboards** offer a user-friendly interface (UI), enabling users to manage connectors without the complexity of using the connector’s API directly.
- **AD4GD Connectors** are central elements of the Dataspace, providing secure, reliable, and structured data exchange between participants.
- **Consumer backend** extends the connector’s data plane by providing functionality to persist transferred assets into a user’s storage such as MinIO.
- **Identity provider (DAPS)** functions as an Identity Access Management (IAM) layer, issuing Dynamic Attribute Tokens (DAT) to authenticated and verified participants, ensuring secure and authenticated connections.
- **Federated Catalogue** it functions as a data broker by enabling participants to find and access data offerings published by others.

To support secure and structured data exchange within the Dataspace, the AD4GD Connector exposes a set of distinct APIs, each designed to serve a specific function within the architecture:

- **Core API (/api)** provides basic operational endpoints, such as health checks and status.

- **Control API (/control)** manages internal communication between the control and data planes. It is primarily used by the data plane to report the outcome of data transfers and to coordinate transfer-related signalling.
- **Management API (/management)** allows for the configuration and management of connector entities, including assets, policies, and contract definitions. It also supports catalogue publishing for making data assets discoverable to other participants.
- **Protocol API (/protocol)** facilitates contract negotiation and inter-connector messaging using standardized exchange protocols. The current default implementation uses the DataSpace Protocol (DSP).
- **Public API (/public)** serves as the data access point during transfers. Access to assets is secured via authorization codes issued during the data transfer phase, ensuring that only authorized consumers can retrieve protected resources.

1.1.1 IMPROVEMENTS FROM PREVIOUS VERSION

As mentioned, the final version of the EDC connector developed in AD4GD introduces several important enhancements to the Dataspace environment. Besides the components' updates on the connectors' baseline tested in the D4.2 scenario that corresponds to the EDC connectors' live project, this new deployment considers two main targets.

One of the key advancements in this iteration is the introduction of the **Federated Catalogue**, which now provides proper data asset discovery, replacing the catalogue functionality previously handled by the ATOS provider connector. The service uses a set of crawlers that periodically query the catalogues exposed by participant EDC connectors, collecting metadata about available data assets. Instead of centralizing the data itself, the Federated Catalogue only gathers metadata describing what data is available and how it can be accessed. This approach allows participants to retain full control over their data while still making it discoverable to others in a structured and interoperable way. The implementation is based on EDC v0.10.1³.

In addition to the Federated Catalogue, this iteration also introduces the integration of an Identity Provider using **DAPS (Dynamic Attribute Provisioning Service)**. DAPS is responsible for issuing and validating identity and access tokens based on participant credentials. By incorporating DAPS, the Dataspace now enforces authenticated and trusted communication between connectors, ensuring that only verified participants can exchange data. This marks a critical step toward aligning with Dataspace security standards and enabling scalable, policy-based access control. The authorization process is based on a centralized OAuth 2.0 authorization framework, with the Dynamic Attribute Provisioning Service (DAPS) acting as the identity provider. The implementation of the identity provider is based on the Sovity DAPS, which is built on Keycloak⁴.

Finally, and oriented to improve the usability of the data connector when define and include new assets, there are several additional functionalities added in this line. These include:

- Support for **static headers, proxy path, and query parameters**: These options allow users to pass required values during data transfer, enhancing flexibility in integrating with target services.
- Support for **protected assets**: Assets can now be secured using credentials, with support for Bearer Tokens and API Keys.

³ <https://github.com/eclipse-edc/Connector>

⁴ <https://github.com/soivity/soivity-daps>

- **Basic policy engine support:** The updated EDC connectors now include a basic policy engine that supports two types of access rules – interval-based policies and claims-based policies (e.g. policy connected with company location claim).
- All EDC-based components (Federated Catalogue, Connector) support access protection **via bearer tokens or API keys**. This feature is currently disabled in the AD4GD deployment to reduce complexity in the demonstrations but can be reactivated when needed.

Finally, the **Connectors' version was upgraded to v0.10.1**, incorporating all relevant improvements and maintaining compatibility with current DataSpace Protocol standard.

1.2 AD4GD DATA SPACE FINAL NODE DEPLOYMENT

The EDC Connector baseline is deployed as a set of interconnected containers. This approach was also followed by AD4GD to build and deploy its connector: open-source components from **Eclipse Foundation**⁵ and **Sovity Community Edition**⁶ were adapted and redistributed as containers to be combined and deployed in a containers' orchestration framework. This framework corresponds to the AD4GD cluster, based on **Kubernetes** as orchestrator, and so, this connector can communicate with the rest of the projects' components, such as its central repository based on MinIO and its Identity Manager, relying on Keycloak. This way, the AD4GD Data connector deployment shares the project's infrastructure described in D5.1 with the AI platform (Figure 4).

Figure 4: AD4GD HPC cluster architecture (from D5.1)

The AD4GD connector instance (replicated in the AD4GD cluster managed by ATOS and in the PSNC cluster) is composed by four main building blocks, deployed and interconnected as shown in Figure 5. These are:

- Core **Connector** deployment, based on Eclipse Dataspace Components represents the core of the Dataspace connector. It requires a dedicated PostgreSQL database to store the set of assets, policies and contracts defined within the scope of the connector instance. It implements the required APIs to expose (and support) the connectors' functionalities, listed in section 1.1.
- Connector's **Dashboard** deployment, built on top of the connector's management API and using the Federated Catalogue API, it provides a friendly web user interface to navigate through the

⁵ <https://github.com/eclipse-edc>

⁶ <https://github.com/sovity/edc-ce>

available offers published in the Federated Catalogue, whilst allows the definition of new assets, policies and contracts. It requires a *Configuration file* to specify the API endpoints (management) of the managed connector instance.

- Sovity's implementation of the Dynamic Attribute Provisioning Service (**DAPS**) based on the Keycloak IAM platform. This component supports the registration of connector nodes in the federation and manages the identification and authentication of involved partners in negotiations and transactions processes.
- **Federated Catalogue** based on EDC components for core functionality, acting as a hub for the catalogues of the registered connectors. It exposes, through the Federated Catalogue API (F. Catalogue, sometimes spelled as F. Catalog), the set of available assets in the federation, identifying the management API of the connector that hosts the required asset. The *Participants* JSON file, included in the *configuration file*, specifies the catalogue endpoints of the registered connector instances.

Figure 5: AD4GD Connector architecture provided by PSNC and deployed by ATOS in project's K8s cluster

The Data Dashboard (Figure 6) interacts with the Connector via the Management API to control data flows and retrieves catalogue information from the Federated Catalogue, presenting it to the user. Acting as a metadata broker, the Federated Catalogue gathers entries from both Provider and Consumer connectors. The Provider Connector exposes assets sourced from AD4GD data repositories, while the Consumer Connector handles negotiation and data transfer with the Provider based on available offers. Once a transfer reaches the 'STARTED' state, the Consumer Backend is triggered, which uses the provided credentials to fetch the data and persist it in storage. To ensure secure and trusted interactions across all components, the Identity Provider resolves authentication tokens and establishes trust relationships between participants and the Federated Catalogue.

Figure 6: Deployment high-level UML diagram

In the final AD4GD Dataspace deployment, the ATOS and PSNC nodes represent fully functional integrations that demonstrate the core capabilities of the Dataspace architecture. The ATOS node operates as both a data provider and the Data Space Authority, hosting the Federated Catalogue, Dynamic Attribute Provisioning Service (DAPS), and the Provider Connector. PSNC node acts as a data consumer, equipped with a Consumer Connector and backend components for data retrieval and storage. Together, these nodes enable a complete data exchange workflow and serve to validate secure, standards-based interoperability between independently managed environments.

Monitoring, logging, and health-check endpoints are configured for each component to support operational observability. Future iterations of the deployment will enable full authentication and access control, to enhance security and align with evolving trust models specifically, transitioning from a centralized trust architecture based on OAuth 2.0 with DAPS to a decentralized approach such as the Decentralized Claims Protocol (DCP).

Final deployment of the AD4GD Dataspace included the federation of catalogues coming from FAIRiCUBE and AD4GD different related initiatives, each of them deploying its own instance of the here presented connector. These are (Figure 2):

- AD4GD cluster connector
- PSNC connector
- EOX - FAIRiCUBE
- NILU - FAIRiCUBE
- RASMADAM - FAIRiCUBE

1.3 AVAILABLE ASSETS

In the dataspace context, an **asset** serves as an abstraction layer over a piece of data or a service that either provides data or performs some form of computation and returns the result. Each asset encapsulates not only the underlying data source or service endpoint but also metadata and system-level details necessary to access, interpret, and manage it. This model allows for a consistent, uniform approach to interfacing with various data and computational resources across the system.

At present, the system supports assets based on the *HttpData* resource type. This type allows integration with any HTTP-accessible data source, offering flexibility in terms of the data format and hosting environment. Supported formats include, but are not limited to, JSON, CSV, and binary data.

When creating an asset using *HttpData*, a key configuration element is the *dataAddress*. This must include a *baseUri*, which points to the endpoint responsible for delivering the data. The endpoint can reside anywhere that is reachable via standard HTTP protocols – it is not restricted to specific storage services like Amazon S3 or Azure Blob Storage. This flexibility allows seamless integration with APIs, internal services, and public data sources.

In addition, assets offer flexible configuration options to define how they can be accessed. This includes support for dynamic extension of the base URI through path segments, query parameters, request bodies, or even HTTP method customization. Such configurability allows us to expose entire APIs as single dataspace assets, making integration and reuse significantly more efficient.

Static HTTP headers can also be defined as part of the asset configuration, which is particularly useful for authentication and custom access patterns. For protected endpoints, the system supports multiple authentication schemes:

- **API Key** – provided as a static header.
- **Basic Authentication** – credentials supplied via static headers.
- **Bearer Token** – configured using dedicated fields in the *dataAddress*. This allows the connector to handle token retrieval and injection automatically when accessing secured resources.

These capabilities enable secure, fine-grained control over how each asset is accessed, without coupling clients tightly to the underlying service implementation.

An important step since the implementation of the basic validated use case in D4.2 is the inclusion of the set of data sources from the AD4GD project: within the implementation of the project's pilots, there are several resources generated that can be potentially converted into assets to be shared with other interested consumers. In a first simple classification, we can distinguish between:

- datasets and files that have been created or transformed within the scope of the project's pilots and are stored in the **AD4GD internal repository**. Here, we consider e.g. CSV files that merge information from different sources, JSON-LD files with harmonised predictions, historical records or AI developed models.
- Data streams or **HTTP** endpoints to **external data sources** (e.g. FROST server) that allows performing data requests or subscriptions and retrieving data on demand.

For all these considered sources, and using the new assets' creation features, the AD4GD and PSNC connectors have define their own set of assets to enrich their corresponding catalogues.

1.3.1 AD4GD MINIO SHARED DATASETS

The AD4GD project manages an internal data repository based in MinIO⁷. This is a high-performance, S3-compatible object storage server designed for large-scale AI/ML, *data lake*, and database workloads. It's a software-defined storage solution that can be deployed on any cloud or on-premises infrastructure. MinIO version used in AD4GD is licensed under the open-source GNU AGPL v3.

As mentioned above, the AD4GD repository stores and serves heterogeneous data files using a standard S3⁸ de-facto standard HTTP REST API. To adapt the EDC assets' definition capabilities to the S3 API requirements, the project has created a python-based HTTP adaptor that authenticates the AD4GD connector instance and configures the request, exposing only selected buckets and files. This adaptor is

⁷ <https://min.io/>

⁸ <https://min.io/docs/minio/linux/reference/s3-api-compatibility.html>

deployed as a container within the AD4GD cluster and exposed internally as an endpoint (reachable only by components deployed within the cluster). This is mapped as an HTTP asset in the AD4GD connector identified as **S3_Client_CSV_File_01** (Figure 7) and configured to allow parameters in the request and retrieve CSV files.

```

{
  "@id": "S3_Client_CSV_File_01",
  "@type": "Asset",
  "properties": {
    "proxyPath": "true",
    "version": "",
    "name": "MINIO_CSV_FILE",
    "proxyQueryParams": "true",
    "id": "S3_Client_CSV_File_01",
    "contentType": "text/csv",
    "baseUrl": "http://edc-connector-s3client-service.edc-connector.svc.cluster.local:8000/dataset"
  },
  "dataAddress": {
    "@type": "DataAddress",
    "proxyPath": "true",
    "type": "HttpData",
    "proxyQueryParams": "true",
    "contentType": "text/csv",
    "header:content-type": "text/csv",
    "baseUrl": "http://edc-connector-s3client-service.edc-connector.svc.cluster.local:8000/dataset"
  }
}

```

Figure 7: AD4GD asset (EDC asset JSON description) to retrieve CSV files from AD4GD internal MinIO repository

Once the negotiation process is finished (as described in D4.2), the asset is exposed through the Public API (AD4GD Connector’s Public Endpoint) allowing **three different parameters** (Figure 8):

- **Bucket** (mandatory): provides the name of the MinIO bucket where the required file is stored
- **Name** (optional): contains the name (and path if needed) of the file to be retrieved. If this parameter is not provided, the request will retrieve a list of the available files in the pointed bucket
- **URL** (optional): if “Name” is provided and URL is set to “true”, the request will retrieve the available **metadata** of the file and a S3 pre-signed URL to directly download the file, valid for 1 hour.

Figure 8: AD4GD - S3_Client_CSV_File_01 - Asset Transfer Process

Each file stored in AD4GD MinIO repository supports metadata definition that can be provided when the file is uploaded or later, using the S3 API. These metadata are stored as “X-AMZ” prefixed attributes, and can be retrieved using the “url = true” in the request (Figure 9):

```

GET 'https://ad4gd-provider-edc.dashboard-siba.store/public?bucket=connector&name=Britzer_Kirchteich-ori.csv&url=True'
header 'Authorization: Token Given by the DAPS'

{
  "object_info": {
    "key": "Britzer_Kirchteich-ori.csv",
    "Storage Class": null,
    "Content-Type": "text/csv",
    "Owner ID": null,
    "version_id": null,
    "metadata": {
      "Accept-Ranges": "bytes",
      "Content-Length": "372766",
      "Content-Type": "text/csv",
      "Date": "Mon, 23 Jun 2025 17:45:37 GMT",
      "Etag": "\"d3ed7cb7650e0c29ef78d9d22fe50798\"",
      "Last-Modified": "Fri, 28 Mar 2025 14:48:20 GMT",
      "Server": "MinIO",
      "Strict-Transport-Security": "max-age=31536000; includeSubDomains",
      "Vary": "Origin, Accept-Encoding",
      "X-Amz-Id-2": "dd9025bab4ad464b049177c95eb6ebf374d3b3fd1af9251148b658df7ac2e3e8",
      "X-Amz-Request-Id": "184BBD0B879A1533",
      "X-Content-Type-Options": "nosniff",
      "X-Ratelimit-Limit": "7770",
      "X-Ratelimit-Remaining": "7770",
      "X-Xss-Protection": "1; mode=block"
    },
    "size": 372766,
    "last_modified": "03/28/2025, 14:48:20"
  },
  "presigned_url": "https://minio-ad4gd-api.dashboard-siba.store/connector/Britzer_Kirchteich-ori.csv?X-Amz-Algorithm=AWS4-HMAC-SHA256&X-Amz-Credential=6zAvNC6Kly3ZiicH1zcn%2F20250623%2Fus-east-1%2Fs3%2Faws4_request&X-Amz-Date=20250623T174537Z&X-Amz-Expires=3600&X-Amz-SignedHeaders=host&X-Amz-Signature=5204b6dc30adf8c8bbe7b549a91290f6dcf07f8148ce38ee19e31458275790e1"
}

```

Figure 9: AD4GD – Example of a data transaction for the - *S3_Client_CSV_File_01* – asset requesting metadata (url = true)

1.3.2 GEONETWORK

Geonetwork's present within the Dataspace brings together diverse environmental and geospatial datasets, including:

- Water temperature and level measurements for numerous Berlin lakes, collected at high frequency from in-situ stations and harmonized for research and management.
- Hydrological and water quality observations in Berlin lakes from citizen science (CrowdWater App).
- Geometries and IDs of Berlin lakes, based on the official Berlin Senate map.
- Surface water conductivity and temperature data from the river Spree.
- Land use and land cover maps of Catalonia, including versions enriched with OpenStreetMap and habitat connectivity indices.
- Camera trap occurrence data from Catalonia for biodiversity and habitat studies.
- Subsets of GBIF mammal's occurrence data.
- Air quality datasets from Sensor. Community, PurpleAir sensors, and Plume Flow devices, providing particulate matter and meteorological parameters.
- ERA5 global reanalysis data and CAMS European air quality reanalyses and forecasts, offering long-term, high-resolution atmospheric and air quality information.
- These datasets are provided in various formats and support environmental monitoring, research, and spatial analysis.

More details about the GeoNetwork catalogue are provided in Section 2.

The EDC connector allows storing metadata which vary with every asset. But there can be extracted the core of repeated metadata entries amongst the datasets. Metadata is stored in *json-ld* format (Figure 10) that provides much flexibility for describing the record and creating dependencies between the records.

```
{
  "@id": <string>,
  "@type": <type of set>,
  "abstract": <string description>,
  "identifier": <identifier>,
  "issued": <date of issued>,
  "language": <3-letter code of language>,
  "publisher": <publisher of data>,
  "title": <title of asset>,
  "updated": <date of update>,
  "dataQuality": <quality of data>,
  "distribution": <list of urls>,
  "granularity": <granularity of data>,
  "theme": <list of themes>
}
```

Figure 10: AD4GD – Geonetwork data asset structure (Metadata)

Dataset has been uploaded to the server via an API service using a custom Jupyter notebook. The notebook parses the file with the metadata and then to consistently send data to custom endpoints set to receive HTTP requests.

1.4 SCALABILITY AND EXPANDABILITY

The AD4GD Data Connector and all its related components (DAPS, Federated Catalogue, Connector's Dashboard and HTTP adaptors) have been developed using open-source code and built as containers,

which make the full deployment completely portable. The deployments of the AD4GD and the PSNC connectors instances have been done on top of a Kubernetes cluster (described in D5.1). Kubernetes⁹ technology implements natively horizontal pod autoscaling and cluster autoscaling features, plus the ability to manage deployments across multiple clusters. These capabilities allow Kubernetes to automatically adjust resources based on-demand, ensuring applications can handle increased traffic and workload. Due to the open-source nature of the code, this infrastructure will be transferred to the SAGE project as the baseline for the GDDS implementation.

⁹ <https://kubernetes.io/docs/concepts/workloads/autoscaling/>

2 DATA AND METADATA CATALOGUE

This section describes the AD4GD data and metadata catalogue implementation within an instance of the open-source GeoNetwork, including practices for documenting ISO 19115-compliant metadata, and the methods used to connect the catalogue with other technical components in the Dataspace, such as accessing it via OGC CSW (Catalogue Service for the Web) and connecting it with other services like OGC Sensor Things API (STA), STApplus (extension of STA), TAPIS (Tables from OGC APIs for Sensors), and the Eclipse Dataspace Connector Federated Catalogue.

The AD4GD project adopted the Data Spaces Support Centre (DSSC) building blocks¹⁰ as a basis to establish the elements required to support the implementation of the GDDS. Metadata catalogues are a fundamental technical building block that provides accessibility and discoverability¹¹. D4.2 included a desk review of the most relevant standards (e.g., ISO 19115¹², DCAT, the GeoDCAT-AP¹³ extension, Dublin Core¹⁴, Schema.org¹⁵, and the Sensor Observation Sample and Actuator (SOSA)¹⁶ model, serialization formats (e.g. Resource Description Framework (RDF)¹⁷, Extensible Markup Language (XML), Turtle¹⁸, and JSON-LD), and catalogue systems in place (e.g., the Radiant Earth STAC Browser¹⁹, the Comprehensive Knowledge Archive Network (CKAN)²⁰, the SpatioTemporal Asset Catalogue (STAC)²¹, and the GeoNetwork²² catalogue). This review provided the necessary context for how AD4GD data can be structured and described in a consistent way using metadata.

This section describes the technologies selected and implemented in AD4GD to support the data and metadata cataloguing. The presented solution provides access to internal users via a cloud based MinIO repository for data storage (and for connector deployment for data sharing) and implements a GeoNetwork ISO19115 metadata catalogue (serving as the master copy and the most comprehensive and detailed metadata in AD4GD) that connects with Data Catalogue Vocabulary (DCAT)²³ metadata that is exposed to the rest of the Dataspace using the Eclipse Dataspace Connectors (EDC) in compliance with IDSA DataSpace Protocol²⁴ as described in the DSSC blueprint²⁵. A decisive factor for adopting GeoNetwork is that most of the data in the project has a geospatial component and the ISO19115 and GeoNetwork are two consolidated technologies in the geospatial world.

In particular, this sections details the structure and access mechanisms for the MinIO data repository (Section 2.2), the implementation of the GeoNetwork catalogue (Section 2.3) and the methods supporting metadata propagation to the EDC federated catalogue (Section 3.3) including a proposal to aggregate metadata from MinIO with the ones created in GeoNetwork to generate enriched asset entries in the EDC federated catalogue of the Dataspace (Section 2.4). Thus, while in D4.2 the focus was on the standards and

¹⁰ <https://dssc.eu/space/BVE2/1071252426/Building+Block+Overview#2.-Data-Spaces-Building-Blocks>

¹¹ <https://dssc.eu/space/BVE2/1071256347/Data,+Services,+and+Offerings+Descriptions>

¹² <https://www.iso.org/standard/26020.html>

¹³ <https://semiceu.github.io/GeoDCAT-AP/releases/>

¹⁴ https://www.dublincore.org/resources/glossary/dublin_core/

¹⁵ <https://schema.org/>

¹⁶ <https://www.w3.org/TR/vocab-ssn/>

¹⁷ <https://www.w3.org/TR/rdf11-concepts>

¹⁸ <https://www.w3.org/TR/turtle/>

¹⁹ <http://schema.org/>

²⁰ <https://ckan.org/>

²¹ <https://stacs-spec.org/>

²² <https://github.com/geonetwork/core-geonetwork/pull/3714>

²³ <https://www.w3.org/TR/vocab-dcat-3/>

²⁴ <https://internationaldataspaces.org/offers/dataspace-protocol/>

²⁵ Data Spaces Blueprint v2.0: <https://dssc.eu/space/BVE2/1071251457/Data+Spaces+Blueprint+v2.0+-+Home>

catalogues review and the establishment of best practices for documenting ISO19115 metadata in GeoNetwork, in this document the focus is on how GeoNetwork metadata is connected to the rest of the components of the Dataspace.

2.1 TAPIS CLIENT APPLICATION FOR DATA AND METADATA FLOW DEMONSTRATIONS IN AD4GD

To demonstrate and illustrate the interaction with the different technical components of AD4GD, an open-source client application named TAPIS (Tables from APIs) has been developed and its source code is openly accessible in GitHub²⁶. TAPIS reads data and metadata from multiple supported APIs and data file formats and organizes the information into structured tables via a node-based interface that facilitates building data workflows interactively. Once the data is imported or retrieved via a URL, it can be directly viewed, edited, semantically enriched, filtered, joint, grouped by, aggregated, etc. as well as presented as bar charts, pie charts, scatter plots, or maps. An overview of TAPIS workspace is depicted in Figure 11.

Figure 11: Workspace of TAPIS²⁷.

TAPIS became an essential tool in AD4GD for conducting interoperability tests and demonstrating data and metadata flows across the Dataspace. TAPIS is under continuous development and new functionalities to support evolving needs are being regularly implemented. In this section of the deliverable, TAPIS will be used to illustrate specific operations and requests performed for accessing and interacting with the different components supporting the AD4GD data and metadata cataloguing.

2.2 AD4GD MINIO DATA REPOSITORY

As mentioned in section 1.3.1, AD4GD provides data access to internal users via a cloud based MinIO server for object data storage. MinIO allows storing vast amounts of data using cloud storage and implements the same API as the Amazon S3 cloud service. In AD4GD, ML and AI processing algorithms were setup in the same cloud infrastructure, so they were trained with the data stored in MinIO to produce new results that were stored in another bucket (a.k.a. directory) in MinIO. In AD4GD, MinIO is the main storage but there are

²⁶ <https://www.tapis.grumets.cat/>

²⁷ <https://www.tapis.grumets.cat/help/#recipes>

two exceptions: the constant sensor data flows stored in a OGC SensorThings API or STApplus using the FROST server IoT Lab implementation^{28,29} and the gridded data organized in an Open Data Cube³⁰ instance using the OGC API coverages³¹. For both exceptions, and when needed, queries to a subset of the data can be performed, with the resulting snapshots potentially stored in the MinIO.

To access to MinIO, authentication is required for all AD4GD users. Access can be performed via the MinIO API³² or via the graphical user interface (GUI) of MinIO called MinIO Console³³. Figure 12 illustrates the MinIO Console object browser of AD4GD.

Figure 12: Overview of MinIO Console object browser of AD4GD³⁴.

Beyond the cloud-based data storage that MinIO offers, a backend for the Dataspace connectors deployment, both for individual files and complete buckets is also used, as described in Section 1.

2.2.1 ACCESSING MINIO FROM TAPIS

Connecting to MinIO and retrieving files can be illustrated with TAPIS. The first step is to connect to the S3 service (Figure 13) by loading the URL of MinIO API (compatible to S3 Services) and using the provided Access and Secret keys facilitated by ATOS which acts as a Dataspace provider.

²⁸ <https://www.iosb.fraunhofer.de/en/projects-and-products/frost-server.html>

²⁹ <https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings3/v1.1/Things>

³⁰ <https://www.opendatacube.org/>

³¹ <https://callus.ddns.net/cgi-bin/mmdc.py>

³² <https://minio-ad4gd-api.dashboard-siba.store/>

³³ <https://minio-ad4gd-console.dashboard-siba.store/browser/>

³⁴ <https://minio-ad4gd-console.dashboard-siba.store/browser/>

Figure 13: Connection to MinIO S3 Service from TAPIS.

The result is a table listing all buckets (directories) available in MinIO, as illustrated in Figure 14.

OGC query URL: <https://minio-ad4gd-api.dashboard-siba.store>

Show row numbers Show self and navigation links

	name	creationDate	href
1	aleale	2025-01-14T11:21:07.607Z	https://minio-ad4gd-api.dashboard-siba.store/aleale
2	connector	2025-01-22T16:19:09.107Z	https://minio-ad4gd-api.dashboard-siba.store/connector
3	miflow	2024-11-14T16:35:53.833Z	https://minio-ad4gd-api.dashboard-siba.store/miflow
4	pilot.1	2024-11-13T16:40:41.197Z	https://minio-ad4gd-api.dashboard-siba.store/pilot.1
5	pilot.1.harmonized	2024-11-13T16:44:31.743Z	https://minio-ad4gd-api.dashboard-siba.store/pilot.1.harmonized
6	pilot.1.internal	2025-03-31T10:29:16.300Z	https://minio-ad4gd-api.dashboard-siba.store/pilot.1.internal
7	pilot.1.predictions	2025-04-02T15:46:38.601Z	https://minio-ad4gd-api.dashboard-siba.store/pilot.1.predictions
8	pilot.1.tmp	2025-02-13T13:11:12.239Z	https://minio-ad4gd-api.dashboard-siba.store/pilot.1.tmp
9	pilot.2.graphab	2025-04-09T10:48:02.437Z	https://minio-ad4gd-api.dashboard-siba.store/pilot.2.graphab
10	pilot.2.internal	2025-03-31T10:29:29.873Z	https://minio-ad4gd-api.dashboard-siba.store/pilot.2.internal
11	pilot.2.test.volume	2025-04-03T20:10:52.132Z	https://minio-ad4gd-api.dashboard-siba.store/pilot.2.test.volume
12	pilot.3	2024-11-14T11:06:39.022Z	https://minio-ad4gd-api.dashboard-siba.store/pilot.3
13	pilot2	2024-11-14T15:02:28.962Z	https://minio-ad4gd-api.dashboard-siba.store/pilot2
14	pilot2bioconn	2024-11-14T16:23:52.727Z	https://minio-ad4gd-api.dashboard-siba.store/pilot2bioconn
15	test-pilot.1	2024-11-13T16:31:50.656Z	https://minio-ad4gd-api.dashboard-siba.store/test-pilot.1
16	test-pilot.2	2024-11-14T16:36:31.318Z	https://minio-ad4gd-api.dashboard-siba.store/test-pilot.2

Figure 14: List of buckets as in MinIO.

Afterwards, it is possible to select a bucket (Figure 15) load it (Figure 16) and extract a table listing the available files within the selected bucket (Figure 17).

Figure 15: Selection of a bucket from TAPIS.

Figure 16: Loading the content of the bucket from TAPIS.

Show row numbers Show self and navigation links

href	lastModified	size	ownerName	storageClass	X-Amz-Meta-Data	X-Amz-Meta-Lake-id	X-Amz-Meta-Project	X-Amz-Meta-Starting-Date
1 https://minio-ad4gd-api.dashboard-siba.store/pilot.1.predictions-siba.store/pilot.1.predictions/predictions_2025-04-20/5800106_predictions_high_precipitations_2025-04-20.jsonld	2025-05-05T13:30:40.496Z	13276	minio	STANDARD	Water Level Predictions	5800106	AD4GD	2025-04-20
2 https://minio-ad4gd-api.dashboard-siba.store/pilot.1.predictions/predictions_2025-04-20/5800106_predictions_no_precipitations_2025-04-20.jsonld	2025-05-05T13:30:38.571Z	13274	minio	STANDARD	Water Level Predictions	5800106	AD4GD	2025-04-20
3 https://minio-ad4gd-api.dashboard-siba.store/pilot.1.predictions/predictions_2025-04-20/5800106_predictions_normal_conditions_2025-04-20.jsonld	2025-05-05T13:30:37.100Z	13203	minio	STANDARD	Water Level Predictions	5800106	AD4GD	2025-04-20
4 https://minio-ad4gd-api.dashboard-siba.store/pilot.1.predictions/predictions_2025-04-20/5800301_predictions_high_precipitations_2025-04-20.jsonld	2025-05-05T13:31:10.212Z	12168	minio	STANDARD	Water Level Predictions	5800301	AD4GD	2025-04-20
5 https://minio-ad4gd-api.dashboard-siba.store/pilot.1.predictions/predictions_2025-04-20/5800301_predictions_no_precipitations_2025-04-20.jsonld	2025-05-05T13:31:09.222Z	12172	minio	STANDARD	Water Level Predictions	5800301	AD4GD	2025-04-20
6 https://minio-ad4gd-api.dashboard-siba.store/pilot.1.predictions/predictions_2025-04-20/5800301_predictions_normal_conditions_2025-04-20.jsonld	2025-05-05T13:31:08.246Z	12091	minio	STANDARD	Water Level Predictions	5800301	AD4GD	2025-04-20
7 https://minio-ad4gd-api.dashboard-siba.store/pilot.1.predictions/predictions_2025-04-20/5800303_predictions_high_precipitations_2025-04-20.jsonld	2025-05-05T13:30:52.496Z	26984	minio	STANDARD	Water Level Predictions	5800303	AD4GD	2025-04-20

Figure 17: Subset of files within the selected bucket.

At this point, a file can be selected using the [select row] option in TAPIS allowing for inspecting the actual data. In the AD4GD MinIO, data exists mainly in CSV and JSON-LD formats (see AD4GD D6.1 and D6.2 for details on the pilot project data). In the following example (Figure 18), the [Import CSV] option to load a CSV file is used to inspect a dataset stored in MinIO (technically the JSON-LD meta can be also loaded and shown as tabular data).

dateTime	high	forecastLow	zero	GT(WaterLevel)	Precipitations
1 2014-05-21	70.00000202959762	70	70.00000202959762	71	0
2 2014-05-22	70.04609995019162	69.93054	69.9202017414227	74	0
3 2014-05-23	70.060995883739	69.82293	69.3842239200974	70	2.2
4 2014-05-24	70.086237692404	69.98059	69.072320216171	79	0.3
5 2014-05-25	70.116795907678	69.951706	68.6968697566263	77	0
6 2014-05-26	70.1167429494989	69.41536	68.8853976229627	77	0
7 2014-05-27	70.126932014621406	69.29271	69.8070510289004	77	11.6
8 2014-05-28	77.00000214576721	77	77.00000214576721	79	19.5
9 2014-05-29	77.4418440178897	77.33771	77.159104446451	87	1.6
10 2014-05-30	77.6584006303547	77.43179	77.0762725501195	63	0
11 2014-05-31	77.7294937595934	77.37495	78.96796120495990	61	0
12 2014-06-01	77.70714632949894	77.23575	78.9202039995192	50	0
13 2014-06-02	77.52898886501312	77.04441	78.464127911377	53	0.2
14 2014-06-03	77.5220816861604	76.83057	78.3930321767657	44	1.7
15 2014-06-04	44.0000017288347	44	44.0000017288347	44	0
16 2014-06-05	42.43468320333888	41.901823	41.725760132074395	44	3.4
17 2014-06-06	41.156468620313843	40.460291	39.98958940289771	46	0

Figure 18: Data in MinIO inspected from TAPIS.

This flow demonstrates the access to MinIO. The entire recipe to access MinIO from TAPIS is available online³⁵. However, the focus of this section of this deliverable is on metadata rather than on the data itself. The next subsection explores the metadata capabilities described in Amazon S3 specification also implemented in MinIO.

³⁵ <https://www.tapis.grumets.cat/help/#recipe08>

2.2.2 METADATA ON MINIO

The files stored in MinIO incorporate a minimum set of metadata information according to the Amazon S3 cloud specification. The metadata can be added to the files stored in MinIO and this metadata is made available when the file is downloaded by including HTTP headers with names that begin with the X-Amz-Meta- prefix. The metadata exposed in MinIO can be seen in Figure 17 above and in detail in the following example for a water level predictions dataset as part of Water Pilot of AD4GD:

- (X-Amz-Meta) **Data**: type of data (e.g. Water Level Prediction)
- (X-Amz-Meta) **Lake_id**: unique identifier of the lake (e.g. 5800310)
- (X-Amz-Meta) **Project**: name of the project (AD4GD)
- (X-Amz-Meta) **Starting-Date**: Starting date for the predictions (2025-05-26)

The number of attributes to be included is unlimited but is limited to a flat structure. This was considered a proof of concept, and more attributes were added for convenience two month before the end of the project. The following screenshot (Figure 19) shows this metadata as exposed in the MinIO.

Figure 19: Metadata exposed in MinIO console.

However, since this is not a standard approach to describe metadata, every time a new AD4GD dataset is made available in MinIO, it is also documented in GeoNetwork metadata catalogue following the ISO19115 standard and then exposed as an asset in the EDC federated catalogue as DCAT³⁶.

2.3 AD4GD GeoNetwork METADATA CATALOGUE

AD4GD adopted the GeoNetwork open-source geospatial catalogue system (version 4.0.6.0) to document all data used and produced by the AD4GD pilot cases. This metadata collection is considered the master copy of the metadata of the data produced by the project.

GeoNetwork offers native support for the ISO19115/ISO19139 geospatial metadata and can export metadata into DCAT format. The AD4GD project specifically adopts the ISO19115:2003 version of the standard, which is widely used worldwide, such as by the European Spatial Data Infrastructure (INSPIRE). At the same time, the GDDS is expected to follow the IDSA recommendations and adopt the DCAT standard.

³⁶ <https://docs.internationaldataspace.org/ids-knowledgebase/dataspace-protocol>

GeoNetwork exposes metadata through the Open Geospatial Catalogue Service for the Web (OGC-CSW)³⁷ and supports retrieving metadata through HTTP requests in both ISO19115/19139 and DCAT standard formats, making it well aligned to the needs of AD4GD and the overall GDDS.

The following requests can be used to retrieve the full AD4GD GeoNetwork catalogue as ISO19115:2003 or as DCAT:

- As ISO19115:2003:
[https://catalogue.grumets.cat/geonetwork/ad4gd/cat/csw?REQUEST=GetRecords&SERVICE=CSW&version=2.0.2&resultType=results&typeNames=gmd:MD_Metadata&namespace=xmlns\(gmd=http://www.isotc211.org/2005/gmd\)&outputSchema=http://www.isotc211.org/2005/gmd&maxRecords=100&elementSetName=full](https://catalogue.grumets.cat/geonetwork/ad4gd/cat/csw?REQUEST=GetRecords&SERVICE=CSW&version=2.0.2&resultType=results&typeNames=gmd:MD_Metadata&namespace=xmlns(gmd=http://www.isotc211.org/2005/gmd)&outputSchema=http://www.isotc211.org/2005/gmd&maxRecords=100&elementSetName=full)
- As DCAT:
[https://catalogue.grumets.cat/geonetwork/ad4gd/cat/csw?REQUEST=GetRecords&SERVICE=CSW&version=2.0.2&resultType=results&typeNames=dcat&namespace=xmlns\(gmd=http://www.isotc211.org/2005/gmd\)&outputSchema=http://www.w3.org/ns/dcat%23&maxRecords=100&elementSetName=full](https://catalogue.grumets.cat/geonetwork/ad4gd/cat/csw?REQUEST=GetRecords&SERVICE=CSW&version=2.0.2&resultType=results&typeNames=dcat&namespace=xmlns(gmd=http://www.isotc211.org/2005/gmd)&outputSchema=http://www.w3.org/ns/dcat%23&maxRecords=100&elementSetName=full)

While requesting a subset of the metadata records is possible, due to the modest volume of the number of datasets produced by AD4GD pilots, this possibility is unnecessary and not illustrated here. At the time of writing, the AD4GD GeoNetwork catalogue contains a total of 38 public records that can be browsed from its GUI³⁸.

An overview of the GeoNetwork catalogue landing page is illustrated in [Figure 20](#).

Figure 20: Overview of AD4GD GeoNetwork catalogue landing page³⁹ (accessed at 06/06/2025).

³⁷ <https://docs.ogc.org/is/12-168r6/12-168r6.html>

³⁸ <https://catalogue.grumets.cat/geonetwork/ad4gd>

³⁹ <https://catalogue.grumets.cat/geonetwork/ad4gd>

2.3.1 ACCESSING GEONETWORK METADATA FROM TAPIS

Figure 21 illustrates how to access the GeoNetwork AD4GD catalogue from the predefined list of OGC WCS services available in TAPIS.

Figure 21: Access to GeoNetwork from an OGC WCS request from TAPIS.

The result of the OGC CSW request returns a table (Figure 22) with the records available in the GeoNetwork catalogue, listed by distributions (URLs to the associated resources in MinIO). At the time of writing, the GeoNetwork catalogue includes a total of 308 distributions. The connection between metadata records in GeoNetwork and the data stored in MinIO will be explained in section 3.3.3.

Show row numbers Show self and navigation links

id	title	dataURL
1 22114f67-cdc5-44ae-8954-0192e0d059af	Biesdorfer Baggersee lake (Station ID: 5800317) - Water level predictions	https://minio-ad4gd-api.dashboard-siba.store/pilot.1/predictions/predictions_2025-04-06/5800317_predictions_no_precipitations_2025-04-06.jsonld
2 22114f67-cdc5-44ae-8954-0192e0d059af	Biesdorfer Baggersee lake (Station ID: 5800317) - Water level predictions	https://minio-ad4gd-api.dashboard-siba.store/pilot.1/hourlyData/waterlevel/5800317_wasserstand_ew_19_01_2025.csv
3 22114f67-cdc5-44ae-8954-0192e0d059af	Biesdorfer Baggersee lake (Station ID: 5800317) - Water level predictions	https://minio-ad4gd-api.dashboard-siba.store/pilot.1/hourlyData/waterlevel/5800317_wasserstand_ew_27_01_2025.csv
4 6231e4ef-368b-444b-86d1-77adf24a9cbd	Biesdorfer Baggersee lake (Station ID: 5800317) - Water temperature and water level data	https://minio-ad4gd-api.dashboard-siba.store/pilot.1/hourlyData/watertemperature/5800317_wassertemperatur_ew_19_01_2025.csv
5 6231e4ef-368b-444b-86d1-77adf24a9cbd	Biesdorfer Baggersee lake (Station ID: 5800317) - Water temperature and water level data	https://minio-ad4gd-api.dashboard-siba.store/pilot.1/hourlyData/watertemperature/5800317_wassertemperatur_ew_27_01_2025.csv

Figure 22: Snapshot of the table displaying all distributions in AD4GD GeoNetwork returned by the OGC WCS request.

2.3.2 PRODUCTION AND MANAGEMENT OF ISO19115 METADATA

The production of rich metadata is crucial for data discovery, access and reuse. All participants in the AD4GD pilot cases have access to the GeoNetwork catalogue to create their metadata records, specifically using the ISO19115:2003 version of the standard. The ISO19115 standard defines an extensive set of metadata elements for describing geographic resources and a subset known as the core metadata elements classified as Mandatory, Optional and Conditional (i.e. required only under specific conditions). While the mandatory elements are enough to ensure compliance with the standard, ISO authors recommend including Optional ones to increase interoperability. In AD4GD each resource is documented using the ISO19115:2003 metadata elements agreed among project participants. The used elements are detailed in Annex I and Table 2.

Despite the rules to create quality metadata offered by ISO specifications, there may be several acceptable ways to describe the same property. Thus, to promote consistency and facilitate the metadata creation process, specific templates have been prepared for each type of data source to describe (Figure 23), as well as a set of best practices to follow have been produced and documented in AD4GD GitHub at <https://github.com/AD4GD/Component-GeoNetwork>. GeoNetwork supports different user roles (e.g., reviewer, editor, and administrator). Within AD4GD, CREA partner was designated as the catalogue

administrator and responsible to ensure that the established best practices are followed and that all metadata records are complete and documented in a consistent way.

Figure 23: AD4GD metadata templates.

In addition to using the ISO templates, metadata records can be created by importing external metadata files (e.g., XML files) or by harvesting records where an instance of GeoNetwork is acting as a client of another catalogue, can use to produce ISO19115/19139 compliant metadata.

2.3.3 LINKING KEYWORDS WITH STANDARD VOCABULARIES

An essential step when documenting metadata in GeoNetwork is the linkage of keywords to standard vocabularies as part of the semantic enrichment flows in AD4GD. Thus, keywords used in ISO19115 are linked to standard vocabularies unique URLs, starting from the Essential Variables (EVs) framework for environmental data descriptions on the OGC RAINBOW Definitions Server⁴⁰ (where EV concepts and ontologies for each AD4GD pilot domain have been defined, as explained in AD4GD D6.2 Pilot Technical Implementation Planning, Implementation and Assessment). When a keyword describing a dataset corresponds to a specific EV, it is linked to the appropriate URL on the OGC RAINBOW by including and filling the `<gmx:Anchor>` element⁴¹ inside of the `<gmd:keyword>` element of the ISO19115:2003/19139XML metadata file. An example of this solution can be seen in the fragment of XML in Figure 24.

```

...More XML...
<gmd:descriptiveKeywords>
  <gmd:MD_Keywords>
    <gmd:keyword>
      <gmx:Anchor xlink:href="https://defs-dev.opengis.net/vocprez-
hosted/object?uri=http%3A//w3id.org/ad4gd/ev/ebv/SP_dis_TER_mammals_BPA"
        xlink:type="simple">EBV Species distributions of terrestrial mammals'
binary presence absence</gmx:Anchor>

```

⁴⁰ <https://defs-dev.opengis.net/vocprez-hosted/vocab/>

⁴¹ While the use of an `<gmx:Anchor>` element within a `<gmd:keyword>` element is not present in the original ISO19115:2003 standard itself, it is introduced and enabled by the ISO 19139:2007 XML implementation of ISO 19115:2003 and continue supported in ISO 19115-1:2014 updated XML schemas, therefore it has been considered that the compliance with ISO19115:2003 is preserved. This practice may seem peculiar, but in fact it is also used by the European Environment Agency (EEA) catalogue as it can be seen here:

[https://sdi.eea.europa.eu/catalogue/srv/cat/csw?REQUEST=GetRecordById&SERVICE=CSW&version=2.0.2&typeNames=gmd:MD_Metadata&namespace=xmllns\(gmd=http://www.isotc211.org/2005/gmd\)&outputSchema=http://www.isotc211.org/2005/gmd&maxRecords=100&elementSetName=full&id=e4fcc5da-e51f-4b66-a9b0-78da0cfd9a15](https://sdi.eea.europa.eu/catalogue/srv/cat/csw?REQUEST=GetRecordById&SERVICE=CSW&version=2.0.2&typeNames=gmd:MD_Metadata&namespace=xmllns(gmd=http://www.isotc211.org/2005/gmd)&outputSchema=http://www.isotc211.org/2005/gmd&maxRecords=100&elementSetName=full&id=e4fcc5da-e51f-4b66-a9b0-78da0cfd9a15)

```
</gmd:keyword>
</gmd:MD_Keywords>
</gmd:descriptiveKeywords>
...More XML...
```

Figure 24: XML fragment showing an EV defined in OGC RAINBOW encoded in an ISO 19115 keyword.

The result in GeoNetwork is presented as clickable items that redirect to the individual definition of the keyword. Figure 25 shows the GeoNetwork visual result of an encoded EV concept to ISO 19115 keyword. Figure 26 shows the EV concept as published in OGC RAINBOW.

Figure 25: Detailed view of a GeoNetwork record⁴² describing and linking to an, in this case, an Essential Biodiversity Variable (EBV)).

⁴² <https://catalogue.grumets.cat/geonetwork/ad4gd/eng/catalog.search#/metadata/73a4ad42-63da-40e3-9658-04218db67279>

The screenshot shows the OGC RAINBOW - Hosted instance interface. The main title is "Species distributions of terrestrial mammals binary presence absence". Below the title, there is a breadcrumb trail: Home / Catalogs / AD4GD project catalog / Collections / Essential Biodiversity Variab... / Items / Species distributions of terrestrial mammals binary presence absence. The main content area displays the metadata for the concept "Essential Biodiversity Variables - codelist class". The metadata includes the following fields:

- URI:** http://w3id.org/ad4gd/ev/ebv/SP_dis_TER_mammals_BPA
- Type:** Essential Biodiversity Variables - codelist class
- Concept:** <https://w3id.org/iadopt/ont/Variable>
- type:** Essential Biodiversity Variables - codelist class
- valid:** <http://www.opengis.net/def/metamodel/ogc-na/status>
- has broader:** [Species distributions](#)
- definition:** The presence/absence of all European terrestrial mammal species within contiguous spatial units (grid cells) across the EU over time.
- is in scheme:** [Essential Biodiversity Variables - codelist scheme](#)

On the right side, there is a section titled "Alternate Profiles" with the subtext "View alternate views & formats". It lists two profiles:

- Alternates Profile:**
 - anot-turtle
 - turtle
 - id-json
 - rdf-xml
 - anot-id-json
- OGC Object Profile (currently viewing):**
 - turtle
 - id-json
 - rdf-xml
 - n-triples
 - anot-id-json

Figure 26: EBV concept as in OGC RAINBOW⁴³.

In other cases, beyond the OGC RAINBOW, AD4GD include links to keywords referred to alternative domain specific vocabularies, such as those provided by the European Environmental Agency Glossary⁴⁴, the generic QUDT⁴⁵, the eLTER⁴⁶ vocabularies and ontologies for long-term ecological monitoring in Europe, or the NVS Climate and Forecast Standard Names⁴⁷ provided by the NERC Vocabulary Server (based on the CF Standard Names⁴⁸ commonly used in NetCDF datasets and climate modelling). Additionally, the thesaurus offered by GeoNetwork according to the GEMET - INSPIRE themes is also used, or the MiraMon Thesaurus based on GEMET and the Spatial Data Infrastructure of Catalonia (IDEC) definitions (used mainly in the Biodiversity Pilot which occurs in the Catalonia region).

External and local thesaurus can be created or imported in GeoNetwork; however in AD4GD we opted to perform these linkages manually, so that each variable concept is added as free text and linked to its definition URL by the person editing the metadata. The association of ISO19115 keywords to community adopted vocabularies and ontologies with consideration to the EV framework is part of the contributions to environmental data standardization of AD4GD.

2.3.4 CONNECTING GEONETWORK WITH THE DATA IN MINIO AND OGC APIs

The connection between ISO19115 metadata records in GeoNetwork and the data stored in MinIO is done via the "associated resources" element, where URLs to assets in MinIO are added both as download links and API paths allowing discovering the MinIO data from GeoNetwork instantly. Additionally, STA/STApplus datastreams or paths to the OGC API Coverages (a façade to the Open Data Cube) are added when appropriate. Figure 27 shows an example of the download links and API paths to MinIO (highlighted with a red-coloured box in) as displayed in GeoNetwork for an example metadata record⁴⁹.

⁴³ https://defs-hosted.opengis.net/prez-hosted/catalogs/hosted.ad4gd/collections/ns6:ebv/items/ebv:SP_dis_TER_mammals_BPA

⁴⁴ <https://www.eea.europa.eu/help/glossary/eea-glossary>

⁴⁵ <https://www.qudt.org/>

⁴⁶ <https://vocabs.lter-europe.net/en/>

⁴⁷ <https://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/P07/current/>

⁴⁸ <https://cfconventions.org/Data/cf-standard-names/current/build/cf-standard-name-table.html>

⁴⁹ <https://catalogue.grumets.cat/geonetwork/ad4gd/eng/catalog.search#/metadata/665f500a-7f5f-445c-9bcc-3182122643cb>

Q Back to home < Previous Next >

Download Display mode

Citizen science observations in the Berlin lakes - CrowdWater data

Subset of hydrological observations in the Berlin metropolitan area captured by citizens using the CrowdWater App (<https://crowdwater.ch>). The data is exported in CSV format from CrowdWater and stored in a MinIO server managed by the AD4GD project.

The data consists on two different types of information:
 -Water level: Numerical value to estimate water level based on physical or virtual gauge
 -Water quality: Answers of a questionnaire (qualitative data)

For both types of information the same attribute table is used (columns left blank if not needed):
 ID, ROOT_ID, LATITUDE, LONGITUDE, CREATED_AT, MODIFIED_AT, PRESELECT_WATER_TYPE, CATEGORY, IMAGE, LAKE_USAGE, LAKE_ACCESS, LAKE_SHORE_STATE, LITTER_IN_WATER, LAKE_SWIM, LAKE_TRANSPARENCY, LAKE_WATER_COLOUR, LAKE_SMELL, LAKE_SHORE_VEGETATION, LAKE_PLANTS_UNDERWATER, FLOATING_LEAVE_PLANTS, DUCKWEED, LAKE_MUSSELS, LAKE_DEADWOOD, LAKE_ANIMALS, LAKE_WATER_LEVEL, LAKE_DRIES_OUT, PHYSICAL_SCALE_UNIT, PHYSICAL_SCALE_LEVEL, SPOTTED_AT, DESCRIPTION

Download and links

 CrowdWater data (Link to MinIO GUI for direct data download)
 The data can be accessed via the MinIO GUI at:
https://minio-ad4gd-console.dashboard-siba.store/browser/pilot.1/crowdwater_data/crowdwater_lakes_berlin.csv

 CrowdWater data (MinIO API endpoint)
 The data can be accessed via the MinIO API at:
https://minio-ad4gd-api.dashboard-siba.store/pilot.1/crowdwater_data/crowdwater_lakes_berlin.csv

Overview

Spatial extent

Resource events

Creation 14.03.2025 09:05

Figure 27: Download links and API paths to MinIO data.

This way, the connection between the repository where the data is stored (MinIO and OGC APIs) and the catalogue that describes the data (GeoNetwork) is achieved. However, the datasets available in the MinIO and OGC APIs are exposed in the EDC federated catalogue as assets documented in DCAT⁵⁰ and, during this process, the ISO19115 metadata documented in GeoNetwork needed to be propagated or will be missed by users connecting to the Dataspace. A solution to propagate GeoNetwork metadata to the EDC federated catalogue was proposed by PSNC and the result is presented in the next subsection.

2.4 PROPAGATING GEONETWORK METADATA IN THE ECD FEDERATED CATALOGUE

The assets for the resources documented in GeoNetwork have been generated in the ECD federated catalogue, available via the following endpoints:

- **EDC Consumer Dashboard (PSNC):** <https://consumer-dashboard-edc-connector.apps.dcw1.paas.psncl.pl>
- **EDC Provider Dashboard (ATOS):** <https://ad4gd-dash-edc.dashboard-siba.store>

Each resource in GeoNetwork has one or more distributions. At the time of performing this metadata conversion, there were 308 distributions. Each distribution was created as an individual asset in the EDC catalogue. Internally, a "metadata" section has been created in the minimum metadata that EDC provides by default. The GeoNetwork metadata was added in an extra property "metadata" of the JSON-LD asset description. In practice, this metadata is a DCAT/Dublin core conversion of the ISO19115.

In order to illustrate this process, the Figure 28 shows an example AD4GD metadata record as exposed in GeoNetwork⁵¹ and the Figure 29 shows a distribution of the same metadata record extracted from the Federated Catalogue of the EDC inspected from TAPIS.

⁵⁰ <https://docs.internationaldataspaces.org/ids-knowledgebase/dataspace-protocol>

⁵¹ <https://catalogue.grumets.cat/geonetwork/ad4gd/eng/catalog/search#/metadata/6231e4ef-368b-444b-86d1-77adf24a9cbd>

Biesdorfer Baggersee lake (Station ID: 5800317) - Water temperature and water level data

This data consists on water temperature and water level measurements for Biesdorfer Baggersee lake in Berlin at hourly basis (15 minute intervals) and on a daily basis, filtered for selected time periods, in both raw (CSV) and harmonized (JSON-LD) formats. The data originates from an In-situ monitoring station and is considered representative of the entire lake. It is made available through the Berlin Wasserportal (<https://wasserportal.berlin.de>). It is stored in a MinIO server and a FROST server managed by the AD4GD project.

Measuring point information

- Station ID: 5800317
- Location (UTM Zone 33N, EPSG:32633):
- Easting: 401403
- Northing: 5817806

Measured parameters

- Water Temperature (°C)
- Water Level (cm)

Generic paths

- MinIO Console: <https://minio-ad4gd-console.dashboard-siba.store/browser/>
- MinIO API: <https://minio-ad4gd-api.dashboard-siba.store/>
- FROST server: <https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings3/v1.1/Things>

Completed

Download and links

Water Temperature (Hourly basis) Raw data
Timestamp 19-01-2025

This dataset consists of raw sensor data in CSV format and can be accessed via the MinIO API at: https://minio-ad4gd-api.dashboard-siba.store/pilot.1/hourlyData/watertemperature/5800317_wassertemperatur_ew_19_01_2025.csv

Overview

Spatial extent

Figure 28: Metadata as exposed in GeoNetwork.

TAPIS
Tables from APIs
or an API Explorer and a Table Manager

Edit record

counterPartyAddress: <https://ad4gd-provider-edc.dashboard-siba.store/protocol>

assetId: 6231e4ef-368b-444b-86d1-77ad724a9cbd_5800317_wasserstand_tw_26_03_2025_jsonld

offerId: Y2RnNjZlMWU0ZWYmZy4yOjNDREllTgZ2ZDElNzhkZGYyNGE5Y2lkXzU4MDAzMTdfd2Fzc2Vyc3RlbnRldHdMjZM

description: Biesdorfer Baggersee lake (Station ID: 5800317) - Water temperature and water level data - 5800317_wasserstand_tw

mediaType: application/json

abstract: This data consists on water temperature and water level measurements for Biesdorfer Baggersee lake in Berlin at hourly basis

updatePeriodicity: irregular

creationDate: 2024-08-15

language: eng

license_1: otherRestrictions

publisher: für Mobilität, Verkehr, Klimaschutz und Umwelt

extent: Polygon((13 5468 52 5014, 13 5468 52 5056, 13 5506 52 5056, 13 5506 52 5014, 13 5468 52 5014))

updateDate: 2025-05-23

quality: All data is gathered from Berlin Wasserportal.

resolution: 100

keyword_1: water temperature

keyword_2: water level

imageUri: https://catalogue.grumets.cat/geonetwork/ad4gd/api/records/6231e4ef-368b-444b-86d1-77ad724a9cbd/attachments/Biesdorfer_Baggersee_lake.jpg

keyword_3:

keyword_4:

keyword_5:

keyword_6:

keyword_7:

keyword_8:

keyword_9:

keyword_10:

keyword_11:

keyword_12:

keyword_13:

keyword_14:

keyword_15:

keyword_16:

keyword_17:

Figure 29: GeoNetwork metadata exposed in the EDC inspected from TAPIS.

Figure 30 shows the individual assets that correspond to each GeoNetwork distribution. For the example record⁵² as they appear in the EDC consumer federated catalogue⁵³.

Figure 30: Metadata as exposed in EDC consumer dashboard catalogue browser.

An example of the ISO19115 metadata converted in the DCAT/Dublin core as inspected from the EDC Federated Catalogue browser is provided in Figure 31. When compared with the same ISO19115 metadata (exposed in Figure 28 and available online⁵⁴), how the ISO19115 fields were inherited by DCAT or Dublin Core metadata elements accordingly presented as JSON-LD can be seen.

```
{
  "http://www.w3.org/ns/dcat#dataQuality": [
    {
      "@value": "All data is gathered from Berlin Wasserportal."
    }
  ],
  "http://www.w3.org/ns/dcat#granularity": [
    {
      "@value": "100"
    }
  ],
  "http://www.w3.org/ns/dcat#keyword": [
    {
      "@value": "36\u00e4ter 36\u00e4ter36atura"
    },
    {
      "@value": "36\u00e4ter level"
    }
  ],
  "http://www.w3.org/ns/dcat#theme": [
    {
      "@id": "https://catalogue.grumets.cat/geonetwork/thesaurus/iso/topicCategory/environment"
    },
    {
      "@id": "https://catalogue.grumets.cat/geonetwork/thesaurus/iso/topicCategory/inlandWaters"
    }
  ],
  "http://purl.org/dc/terms/abstract": [
    {
      "@value": "This data consists on 36\u00e4ter 36\u00e4ter36atura and 36\u00e4ter level measurements for Biesdorfer Baggersee lake in Berlin at hourly basis (15 minute intervals) and on a daily basis, filtered for selected time periods, in both raw (CSV) and harmonized (JSON-LD) formats. The data originates from an in-situ monitoring station and is"
    }
  ]
}
```

⁵² <https://catalogue.grumets.cat/geonetwork/ad4gd/eng/catalog.search#/metadata/6231e4ef-368b-444b-86d1-77adf24a9cbd>

⁵³ <https://consumer-dashboard-edc-connector.apps.dcw1.paas.psnec.pl>

⁵⁴ <https://catalogue.grumets.cat/geonetwork/ad4gd/eng/catalog.search#/metadata/6231e4ef-368b-444b-86d1-77adf24a9cbd>

```

considered representative of the entire lake. It is made available through the Berlin Wasserportal
(https://wasserportal.berlin.de). It is stored in a MinIO server and a FROST server managed by the AD4GD
37äter37a.\n\nMeasuring point information\n-Station ID: 5800317\n-Location (UTM Zone 33N, EPSG:32633):\n-Easting:
401403\n-Northing: 5817806\n\nMeasured parameters\n-Water Temperature (°C)\n-Water Level (cm)\n\nGeneric paths\n-Path
to MinIO GUI enviroment: https://minio-
ad4gd-api.dashboard-siba.store/\n-Path to FROST server:
https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings3/v1.1/Things?\$filter=substringof\('Wasserportal Berlin - Water Temperature',name\)
}
],
"http://purl.org/dc/terms/accrualPeriodicity": [
  {
    "@value": "irregular"
  }
],
"http://purl.org/dc/terms/issued": [
  {
    "@value": "2024-08-15"
  }
],
"http://purl.org/dc/terms/language": [
  {
    "@value": "eng"
  }
],
"http://purl.org/dc/terms/license": [
  {
    "@value": "otherRestrictions"
  },
  {
    "@value": ""
  }
],
"http://purl.org/dc/terms/publisher": [
  {
    "@id":
    "https://catalogue.grumets.cat/geonetwork/organization/Senatsverwaltung%2520f%25C3%25BCr%2520Mobilit%25C3%25A4t%252C%
    2520Verkehr%252C%2520Klimaschutz%2520und%2520Umwelt"
  }
],
"http://purl.org/dc/terms/spatial": [
  {
    "@id": "._:Nd3f41f5daf1246ee81d447b09e98031f",
    "@type": [
      "http://www.opengis.net/rdf#Polygon"
    ],
    "http://www.opengis.net/rdf#asWKT": [
      {
        "@value": "<http://www.opengis.net/def/crs/OGC/1.3/CRS84>\n          Polygon((13.5468 52.5014, 13.5468
        52.5056, 13.5506 52.5056, 13.5506 52.5014, 13.5468 52.5014))"
      }
    ]
  }
],
"http://purl.org/dc/terms/updated": [
  {
    "@value": "2025-05-23"
  }
],
"http://xmlns.com/foaf/0.1/thumbnail": [
  {
    "@id": "https://catalogue.grumets.cat/geonetwork/ad4gd/api/records/6231e4ef-368b-444b-86d1-
    77adf24a9cbd/attachments/Biesdorfer_Baggersee_from_CrowdWater_with_credits.jpg"
  }
]
}

```

Figure 31: Detailed view of the DCAT/Dublin core conversion of the ISO19115.

To be fully implemented, it would be necessary to provide the metadata in their own asset fields and aligned with the recommendations/agreements of the Dataspace metadata schema. However, this metadata propagation is a proof of concept that demonstrates the AD4GD node of the Dataspace is operating in a way conformant with the IDSA recommendations, while offering a practical solution considering that the GeoNetwork catalogue is a broadly system used to document environmental data worldwide (as with the INSPIRE) and can maintain this role within the GDDS.

2.5 PROPOSAL TO AGGREGATE METADATA FROM MINIO WITH THE ONE INHERITED FROM GEONETWORK TO CREATE SEVERAL ASSETS IN THE EDC

In the case of IoT data measuring, the lakes in Berlin AD4GD stored raw data, harmonized data (with semantic uplift) and Machine Learning based predictions of the same variable. All this data is calculated every week and stored in MinIO and exposed in the Dataspace Federated Catalogue. The metadata of the time series exists only once in GeoNetwork (as a product level) but it can be extracted and linked to the mini-metadata in MinIO (using the X-Amz-Meta-Data and X-Amz-Meta-Lake_id as a join fields) and adding the date coming from X-Amz-Meta-Starting-Date. This metadata is then exposed as part of the asset descriptions in the “metadata” fields. This way we can automatically replicate the metadata created in GeoNetwork in the Dataspace ECD Federated Catalogue and allow for external users in the rest of the Dataspace to discover and use the asset, if they have the right contract allowing them to do so. In a similar way, the OGC API Coverage is exposed in the Dataspace with the metadata describing the datacube products coming from the GeoNetwork. The following Figure 32 illustrates the flow of data and metadata. It is important to note that the metadata is duplicated in the catalogue, but the data is accessed by the control plane directly from the STAplus, MinIO or the OGC API coverage.

Figure 32: AD4GD data and metadata flow.

3 DATA TRUSTWORTHINESS FRAMEWORK

The Data Trustworthiness Framework (DTF), defined in D4.2, is a methodology for assessing and describing the trustworthiness of datasets consumed and produced by AD4GD. This section presents practical examples from the pilot projects of the application of the DTF. It includes an assessment of the reliability of citizen science derived water quality data as part of pilot 1, novel intercomparisons between machine learning derived biodiversity connectivity measures and traditional approaches as part of pilot 2, and new IoT air quality sensor correction models presented as part of pilot 3. More information about the AD4GD pilots can be found on D6.2.

In this section we start by presenting an exploratory, alternative Dataspace approach based on an immutable data catalogue developed within the AD4GD project to later present the DTF applications in the pilots.

3.1 INTEGRITY, PROVENANCE, TRUST AND FACTS

Integrity, Provenance, and Trust (IPT) are essential elements of a resilient data service, offering significant value for both clients and services by ensuring data reliability, traceability, and trustworthiness for data. Maintaining integrity involves efforts to ensure that data remains unaltered by unauthorized users or accidental errors, preserving its intended state for reliable use. Provenance captures the data's lineage, recording every change and who made those changes, which verifies the accuracy, completeness, and consistency of the data over time and across various formats. Trust is established through the use of authoritative, analysis-ready data and maintained across the data lifecycle when combined with the Integrity and Provenance components. Together, these elements create a trustworthy data and services. In this section we propose an alternative architecture to the conventional one proposed by the International Data Space Association that substitutes the need for the Dataspace connectors in general and the EDC in particular. This alternative to a Dataspace implements IPT and it is called FACTS that stands for:

Federated: Many organizations participate

Agile: The cumbersome hub-and-spoke model of traditional attribute and data exchange is replaced by a(n) (eco)system where credential definitions are driven by need with flexibility.

Collaborative: All trusted organizations can use the ecosystem

Trusted: Each participating organization can create trusted assets (data product, services, etc.)

System: The computers, services, endpoints, etc. that bring it all together

FACTS was implemented by Secure Dimensions as part of an exploratory subcontract that CREAM has with them in the AD4GD project.

The first component in this architecture is an Immutable catalogue. This catalogue is based on blockchain technologies, and it is implemented based on the Open Source Hyperledger-Fabric project. The Fabric distributed ledger is designed to record provenance as transactions on the ledger and supports the implementation of an immutable catalogue. The immutable catalogue ensures that the metadata record representing an asset cannot be tampered with and its integrity is preserved. This is an intrinsic property of blockchain technology, where items and steps recorded in the blockchain cannot be deleted but only modified by recording new steps. As part of the metadata, a hash calculated with the actual data can also be saved. In this case, the integrity of the data represented by the metadata can also be ensured, as the hash can be recalculated from the data and compared with the one stored in the metadata. If there is a match between the hash in the catalogue and the recalculated hash, the asset is genuine and has not been

tempered with. The hashes selected in this case are calculated with the Blake3 algorithm. Once data instances are registered in the immutable catalogue, they become a genuine record that allows IPT enablement for the associated data instance. The immutable catalogue will be complex to access from the blockchain directly, but FACTS implementation offers a STAC interface where assets in the blockchain are presented as resources in collections accessible with an API.

← → ↻ 🔍 https://immutable-catalog.dataspace.secd.eu/stac/collections/sensorthings_provenance ☆ 📄 ⬇️ 🗺️ ⋮

SensorThings Dataspace Immutable Catalog

in Catalogue ↑ Up 🗺️ Browse 🔍 Search 📄 API 🔗 Source 🔗 Share 🗺️ Language: English ▾

Description

This catalog contains provenance records produced by <https://processes.dataspace.secd.eu>

License proprietary
Temporal Extent 2025-03-02 12:00:00 UTC until present

Items

🔍 Show Filters

7833814c-157e-48f4-8c23-7c4f8cb554e3
2024-01-13 08:48:37 UTC – 2025-03-23 08:05:11 UTC

83e760f8-0a57-41fb-baee-badeea4807d5
2017-12-31 23:00:00 UTC – 2025-06-17 08:00:00 UTC

Figure 33: Example of one of the collections offered by the STAC catalogue.

7833814c-157e-48f4-8c23-7c4f8cb554e3

API Source Share Language: English

in Catalogue Up Collection Browse Search

Collection

SensorThings Dataspace Immutable Catalog
This catalog contains provenance records produced by https://processes.dataspace.secd.eu 2025-03-02 12:00:00 UTC until present

Metadata

General

Authors	Long John Silver																		
Time of Data	2025-06-17 9:15:09 UTC																		
Time of Data ends	2025-03-23 8:05:11 UTC																		
File Hash	843829a1878b417eaf0953d5be3561fe3f0ada601ed48e5aaad1ea373600a906																		
File Size	262144																		
Hash Alg	BLAKE3																		
Input Uri	https://ctiobs.demo.secure-dimensions.de/staplustest/v1.1/Datastreams(1799)/Observations?Sorterby=id desc&\$top=100																		
Licenses	Definition: https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/3.0/deed.en Name: CC BY 3.0																		
Observed Properties	Definition: http://vocabs.lter-europe.net/EnvThes/22035 Name: temp																		
Time of Data begins	2024-01-13 8:48:37 UTC																		
Statistics	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Name</th> <th>Total</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>FeaturesOfInterest</td> <td>1</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Observations</td> <td>100</td> </tr> <tr> <td>ObservedProperties</td> <td>1</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Parties</td> <td>1</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Licenses</td> <td>1</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Datastreams</td> <td>1</td> </tr> <tr> <td>MultiDatastreams</td> <td>0</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Locations</td> <td>100</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Name	Total	FeaturesOfInterest	1	Observations	100	ObservedProperties	1	Parties	1	Licenses	1	Datastreams	1	MultiDatastreams	0	Locations	100
Name	Total																		
FeaturesOfInterest	1																		
Observations	100																		
ObservedProperties	1																		
Parties	1																		
Licenses	1																		
Datastreams	1																		
MultiDatastreams	0																		
Locations	100																		
IssuerDID	did:sov:Pwgx5wggjG83amuH9SRWs																		
IssuerName	Secure Dimensions																		
HashAlg	BLAKE3																		
HashValue	843829a1878b417eaf0953d5be3561fe3f0ada601ed48e5aaad1ea373600a906																		

Asset

GeoPackage

Preferred FACTS_API_Key FACTS_Browser_Cookie

GeoPackage

Download Copy URL

In order to download the asset via the API, you first need to fetch an API-Key token via https://wallet.dataspace.secd.eu/connections/select which must be submitted as HTTP Header X-FACTS-Key with the asset URL from Copy URL.

Metadata

General

Auth

Refs: apiKey
Roles: download
Schemes:
Description: X-FACTS-Key represents the connection between your Wallet and the Asset Controller to request proof of required FACTS Certificates.
Flows:
AuthorizationCode:
AuthorizationApi: https://wallet.dataspace.secd.eu/user/x-facts-key
Method: get
Parameters:
Expires In:
Description: the validity of the token in seconds
In: query
Required: true
Schema:
Examples: 300
Type: string
ResponseField: x-facts-key
In: header
Name: X-FACTS-Key
Required: true
Type: apiKey

Figure 34: Example of a single resource (a GeoPackage resource) that is available as trusted resource. Last entry in the right column is the hash of the data to validate integrity.

FACTS implements smart certificates that are issued by entrusted entities to the users of the system. These certificates can be considered contracts between the user and the data producer. The main difference with the conventional architecture proposed by the IDSA is that these certificates (equivalent to contracts) are pre-negotiated with the entrusted issuers and stored in the wallet of the user (instead of in the Dataspace Connectors). This way, the certificates are presented by the user directly to the data producer at the moment of requesting access to or processing of assets avoiding any flow of personal/private information to other entities involved. The producer validates the certificates to verifiers before releasing the asset. This implementation is more respectful with GDPR, in particular if users are not acting as part of an organization but as individuals where privacy rules apply.

Data producers remain in control of their data as certificates can be revoked at any time. To ensure total sovereignty of the data to its producer, it is possible to issue a certificate that only allow for data processing but not for data downloading. In this case, trusted services are services that process data and only execute operations after verifying the integrity of the data and the validity of the processing certificates provide by the user. Only the result of the service execution is made available to the user but not the original source data. Again, the producer can request the revocation of the certificate at any time, preventing the data for being further processed.

After experimenting and demonstrating with FACTS in AD4GD, we are convinced that FACTS could serve as a federated alternative to the traditional Dataspace infrastructures more respectful with GDPR.

3.2 PILOT 1 WATER QUALITY

As discussed in D4.2 and multiple other deliverables, Pilot 1⁵⁵, focuses on developing tools and indices to monitor and improve the management of small urban lakes, which play vital ecological and recreational roles but are often neglected in traditional water monitoring frameworks. Due to Berlin's rapid urbanization and climate change, these lakes face increasing challenges from pollution, nutrient loads, and water scarcity, exacerbated by stormwater runoff and fluctuating groundwater influence. The pilot creates a Water Quality Index (WQI) and Water Availability Index (WAI) by combining data from satellite observations, IoT sensors, and Citizen Science inputs with AI-driven analytics. These indices will help stakeholders –ranging from city officials to citizens– prioritize interventions, monitor long-term trends, and make informed decisions to support sustainable lake ecosystems (see Figure 35). The goal is to provide a scalable solution that can enhance water management in Berlin and be transferred to similar urban environments.

Figure 35: Simplified data flow diagram for pilot 1 showing input data sources, scenario modelling, computed indices and a UI showing some of this data to end users.

During the project, citizen science proved to be very promising for gathering basic information about small lakes. Wherever the resolution of satellite data is insufficient or a large part of the water body is covered by tree crowns and sensors are too expensive and too time-consuming to maintain, citizen science data is often the only way to collect data continuously. A questionnaire was created specifically for small urban lakes to be used in the CrowdWater⁵⁶ app. The questions can be answered without in-depth knowledge of water bodies and have been translated into 18 languages. As with many citizen science projects, the

⁵⁵ <https://github.com/AD4GD/pilot-1>

⁵⁶ <https://crowdwater.ch/en/what-is-crowdwater/>

observations provided by citizens are often subjective. For example, a question about the colour of the water may be answered with green or brown, depending on the person, and the question of whether one would swim in the water involves a great deal of subjective assessment. At KWB, a targeted evaluation of the answers was developed to obtain indicators on the nutrient situation, the lake biotope, usage, and water requirements. To calculate the indicator for the nutrient situation, selected answer options are assigned positive (low nutrients) or negative (high nutrients) points. The detailed scoring system is listed in Table 1

Low nutrients indicators		High nutrients indicators	
Go Swimming	+ 1	Transparency 20 – 50 cm	- 1
Transparency > 1m	+ 1	Transparency a few cm	- 2
Floating leaf plants	+ 1	Surface ½ covered by duckweed	- 0,5
Underwater plants	+ 1	Surface ¾ covered by duckweed	- 1
Water colour: blue or clear	+ 1	Surface completely covered by duckweed	- 2
		Water colour: green or brown	- 1
		Water smell: rotten eggs	- 1
		Water smell: Other sewage smell	- 2

Table 1 Scoring system used for the CrowdWater nutrient indicator

The sum of all points results in the indicator. If several observations were made for a lake, the average value is calculated. An overview of the distribution of the nutrient indicator across Berlin's lakes is shown in Figure 36. Lakes that are heavily eutrophicated can be quickly identified in dark red.

Figure 36: Overview of the nutrient indicator for small lakes in Berlin.

It is essential to check how reliably the indicators work despite the subjective data basis. For this purpose, two lakes were selected and observed several times. One is the *Ententeich* in Berlin Schöneberg, which was recorded by the consortium during an AD4GD project meeting on April 8, 2025, and the other is the *Grundwasserteich* in Berlin's Tiergarten, which was observed a total of six times between August 27, 2024, and June 27, 2025.

As seen in Figure 37, there are certainly fluctuations between the assessments, partly due to subjective perception. For the groundwater pond, a possible temporal dynamic is also a factor. Nevertheless, the groundwater pond can clearly be identified as more eutrophicated.

In conclusion, even if the actual value of the indication may fluctuate depending of the citizens observing it, we can still extract comparative information and determine what lake is more eutrophicated allowing decision makes with limited resources to prioritize which lakes require interventions more urgently.

Figure 37: Boxplot of the nutrient indicators for Grundwasserteich and Ententeich based on single observations.

3.3 PILOT 2 BIODIVERSITY

Pilot 2⁵⁷ focuses on advancing biodiversity conservation by evaluating functional landscape connectivity (FLC) in Catalonia, Spain. Recognizing the significance of ecological connectivity for species migration and healthy ecosystems, this pilot aligns with global and European biodiversity strategies, including the European Green Deal and the EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030. It aims to provide scalable, FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) data tools to assess and enhance landscape connectivity, supporting informed decision-making among stakeholders, from policymakers to local biodiversity initiatives. To achieve this, Pilot 2 integrates satellite, administrative, and Citizen Science data with analysis to deliver actionable insights into ecological corridors and species movement (see Figure 38).

⁵⁷ <https://github.com/AD4GD/pilot-2>

Pilot 2 - Biodiversity

AD4GD

Figure 38: Simplified data flow diagram for pilot 2 showing the input data used at different stages of the pipeline.

To analyse differences between the ground-truth and ML modelled habitat connectivity, Mean Squared Error (MSE), Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE), Mean Absolute Error (MAE), Structural Similarity Index (SSIM) indices have been calculated. For forest land cover type with low spatial resolution, there exist moderate differences between ground-truth and predicted habitat connectivity (MSE, RMSE, MAE vary from 0.15 to 0.39). However, mean SSIM value of 0.48-0.49 suggests significant differences in structure between two images. Interquartile Range (IQR) of 0.49 demonstrates the high variability of SSIM values across images. Additionally, roughly a fifth of image pixels have almost random similarity (SSIM < 0.2). However, much better performance has been observed for other habitats, such as aquatic, with their IQR parameter being approximately 33-0.34, while only about 8.8% of pixels show significantly low similarity (SSIM < 0.2) (see Figure 39).

Figure 39: Connectivity maps computed using an ML model and using Graphab. At this level of detail, the differences are not perceptible other than some edge effects in the ML output.

Additionally, models developed for raster datasets with a spatial resolution of 30 m, are significantly more effective (Figure 40). As an illustration, forest habitats at high-scale resolution are described by high (0.88-0.89) SSIM values and low (0.062-0.064) MSE values.

Figure 40: Mean Squared Error (MSE), Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE), Mean Absolute Error (MAE), Structural Similarity Index (SSIM) for Forest habitats, separated by spatial resolution (30m or 390m) and year (1987 or 2022).

Looking at Figure 40, pairs of ground truth and predicted forest connectivity with higher spatial resolution (on the right) consistently show the higher SSIM and lower MSE, RSME, MAE values. Because large-scale computations of ground-truth data take significant time while models achieve better performance, they highlight the value of developed large-scale predictions. See additional comparisons in Figure 41.

Figure 41: Structural similarity index measure (SSIM) spatial distribution and other indices of connectivity predictions (Habitat: Forests, Year: 2012)

No significant variations between timestamps of the same habitats with the same spatial resolution were observed, which allows us to conclude that the temporal differences between the predicted and ground truth are consistent.

Considering significant variations in MSE, RMSE, MAE, and SSIM, validation of output images describing habitat connectivity should be based on a set of indices, rather than relying on a single metric.

3.4 PILOT 3 AIR QUALITY

Pilot 3 focusses on evaluating the potential usefulness of IoT derived air quality data for future forecasting applications. The IoT dataset, the majority of which is derived from the Sensor.Community (formerly Luftdaten) project, is standardised, analysed for outliers and constrained or scaled using the Copernicus Atmosphere Monitoring Service (CAMS) air quality forecast analysis data.

For the rescaling, a machine learning model with meteorological variables (e.g. from the ERA5) is trained. The scaled data are then finally compared with in situ reference measurements from official air quality monitoring stations of various European environmental authorities provided by the European Environment Agency (EEA) (see Figure 42). The focus of this activity is mainly on aerosol air pollutants such as “coarse” particulate matter (PM10) and fine particulate matter (PM2.5).

Figure 42: Simplified data flow diagram for pilot 3.

3.4.1 UPDATED CORRECTION OF IoT MEASUREMENTS

In the previous version of the correction model presented in D4.2, we applied a statistical adjustment to IoT PM observations by rescaling them based on co-located reference measurements from EEA stations. The correction was informed by large-scale spatiotemporal averages from CAMS European air quality analyses and involved predicting a logarithmic scaling factor ($\ln(\alpha)$) using a machine learning model (XGBoost⁵⁸) trained on meteorological data such as temperature, relative humidity, and surface pressure. While this approach was effective in reducing systematic biases, particularly in summer months when

58 <https://github.com/dmlc/xgboost>

Chen, Tianqi; Guestrin, Carlos (2016). "XGBoost: A Scalable Tree Boosting System". In Krishnapuram, Balaji; Shah, Mohak; Smola, Alexander J.; Aggarwal, Charu C.; Shen, Dou; Rastogi, Rajeev (eds.). Proceedings of the 22nd ACM SIGKDD International Conference on Knowledge Discovery and Data Mining, San Francisco, CA, USA, August 13-17, 2016. ACM. pp. 785–794. arXiv:1603.02754

underestimation was common, it was limited by the spatial matching of CAMS Europe grid cells and EEA stations. It also did not account for local particularities such as differences in particulate matter sources.

To address these limitations, we developed an updated correction model that incorporates spatial data aggregation and improved learning techniques. The revised approach begins by clustering IoT sensors using the “Ordering points to identify the clustering structure” (OPTICS) algorithm⁵⁹, requiring a minimum of 50 IoT stations to form a cluster. This step identifies spatial groups of sensors with similar measurement characteristics (see Figure 43). Within each cluster, we average both IoT and reference data to suppress random noise and stabilize the training signal. The usefulness of the cluster is evaluated by checking whether enough reference stations, at least two, lie within the convex hull of the cluster. This ensures that the reference data can be meaningfully compared to the corresponding IoT measurements.

Figure 43: Distribution of labelled and unlabelled IoT stations from the Sensor.Community network across Europe

The core correction model remains based on XGBoost but now benefits from more structured training data. It predicts reference PM values using raw IoT observations along with ERA5 meteorological variables such as 2m air temperature, relative humidity, boundary layer height, and surface pressure. Additional input features include the day of the year and the cluster identifier. This setup enables the model to learn the specific characteristics of each IoT-EEA cluster, allowing it to capture both seasonal effects and spatial heterogeneity (see Figure 44). The model is trained on data from 2017 to 2021, validated on 2022 data, and tested on observations from 2023. It performs well for daily measurement data and achieves an R^2 of approximately 0.89.

⁵⁹ Ankerst, Mihael, Markus M. Breunig, Hans-Peter Kriegel, and Jörg Sander. “OPTICS: ordering points to identify the clustering structure.” ACM SIGMOD Record 28, no. 2 (1999): 49-60.

Schubert, Erich, Michael Gertz. “Improving the Cluster Structure Extracted from OPTICS Plots.” Proc. of the Conference “Lernen, Wissen, Daten, Analysen” (LWDA) (2018): 318-329.

Figure 44: SHAP value statistics of the XGBoost model highlighting the importance of the different input features on the final output.

The updated model effectively captures physical effects such as the hygroscopic growth of aerosols, which varies by season and pollution regime. For example, the correction learns the stronger relative humidity dependence observed in winter, when heating-related emissions are more prominent (see Figure 45).

Figure 45: Distribution of SHAP value for relative humidity as function of input relative humidity coloured according to input IoT PM2.5 measurement values.

Once trained, the model is applied to correct IoT time series. For sensors that belong to a known cluster, the corresponding model prediction is used directly. For sensors outside of any defined cluster, corrected values are estimated using an inverse distance weighted ensemble of predictions from all available clusters (see an example in Figure 46). This approach ensures spatial continuity and enables reliable correction even in regions with sparse or missing reference data.

Figure 46: Demonstration of effectiveness of correction model for cluster representative for Brussels for winter 2022/23 (top panel) and summer 2023 (bottom panel).

Overall, the updated correction framework offers greater robustness, scalability, and transferability than the original method.

3.4.2 VALIDATION OF GRIDDED PRODUCTS BASED ON CORRECTED IOT DATA

To evaluate the quality of the high-resolution PM dataset derived solely from corrected IoT sensor data, we conducted a Europe-wide validation using independent reference measurements from EEA air quality stations. The gridded products are constructed by interpolating corrected IoT observations to a regular grid with a spatial resolution of $0.01^\circ \times 0.01^\circ$, covering the period from 2017 to 2024.

The validation shows that the IoT-only dataset captures both spatial patterns and temporal variability of PM concentrations with good accuracy. Performance is especially strong in regions with higher sensor density, such as Central Europe, where the agreement with EEA reference data is consistently high (see Figure 47 and Figure 48). The dataset also performs well across different station types and area classifications, including both urban and rural settings (see Figure 49).

Figure 47: Skill scores of intercomparison between gridded IoT-only product and EEA reference stations. Left: Bias; centre: RMSE; right: mean normalized bias.

Figure 48: Histograms of mean normalized bias between gridded IoT-only product and EEA reference stations as well as CAMS Europe analysis and EEA reference stations. Separation into station type according to categorization of EEA.

Figure 49: Same as Figure 48, but now separated by area type.

By comparing interpolated grid values with collocated reference observations, we find that the corrected IoT-only product significantly improves upon uncorrected sensor data. The model is able to reproduce daily fluctuations and reduces systematic biases that were previously observed, particularly under varying seasonal and meteorological conditions.

These results demonstrate that, when properly corrected and quality-controlled, low-cost IoT measurements are capable of supporting the generation of high-resolution air pollution maps. The IoT-only gridded dataset provides a valuable observational layer that complements traditional monitoring networks and is well-suited for applications such as air quality assessment, model evaluation, and environmental health analysis.

CONCLUSIONS

This document presents WP4 “Satellite and Green Deal Data Space Integration”, including tasks 4.2 “Green Deal Data Space Implementation”, 4.3 “Green Data Space integration with third-party services” and 4.4 “Ground truthing and data trustworthiness framework”. It also has overlap with and incorporates work from the three pilot projects within WP6 and the machine learning work being done in WP5.

Section 1 details the evolution of the AD4GD data connector features following the data connector. This deployment demonstrates the capabilities of the data connector approach to building the Green Deal Data Space, in accordance with IDSA requirements and as implemented by the Eclipse Data Connector. In the final version of the deployment, the FAIRiCUBE and AD4GD has created of a single Dataspace integrating assets from both projects going beyond what was foreseen in the DoA of this project. Even if the Connector approach works as described, and implements contracts to ensure who can access what, it lacks some essential characteristics that should make data more trustable. In section 3.1, we present an exploratory, alternative Dataspace approach called FACTS that is based on an immutable data catalogue developed within the AD4GD project. This approach implements certificates that are owned by the participants directly making the implementation conformant with GDPR and implements immutable assets allowing for trusting the data (providing a mechanism to ensure it has not been tempered with).

Section 2: *Data and Metadata Catalogue*, describes how the different data and metadata catalogues in the project can be connected and harmonized. In AD4GD the metadata master copy is maintained in GeoNetwork this links to the data distributions (including MinIO repositories and OGC APIs) as well as how to present this metadata in the Eclipse Data Connector Federated Catalogue. In addition, practices for documenting ISO 19115-compliant metadata were defined. All this was presented in the AGILE conference 2025⁶⁰.

Section 3: *Data Trustworthiness Framework*, demonstrates the applicability of the framework for assessing data quality as defined in D4.2 in practical examples from the pilots of the application. These include: an assessment of the reliability of citizen science derived water quality data as part of the “Berlin Lakes pilot”, novel intercomparisons between machine learning derived biodiversity connectivity measures and traditional approaches as part of the “Biodiversity pilot”, and new IoT air quality sensor correction models presented as part of “Air quality pilot”.

⁶⁰ Maso J, Brobia A, Palma R, and Ignacio EliceGUI I (2025, June) Making Geospatial Data Offerings Discoverable and Accessible in the Green Deal Data Space. DOI: 10.5194/agile-giss-6-38-2025. In Internet: <https://agile-giss.copernicus.org/articles/6/38/2025/>

ANNEX I

The following Table 2 presents the ISO 19115 core metadata elements in relation with those used to document AD4GD pilot datasets.

ISO19115 element	Domain	Description	Obligation	Present in AD4GD metadata
Dataset title	MD_DataIdentification.citation > CI_Citation.title	Title of the dataset	Mandatory (M)	Yes
Dataset reference date	MD_DataIdentification.citation > CI_Citation.date	Date of the metadata record creation, revision, etc	Mandatory (M)	Yes
Dataset responsible party	MD_DataIdentification.pointOfContact > CI_ResponsibleParty	Party who authored/owns/supplies/is responsible/has processed/has published the resource	Mandatory (M)	Yes
Geographic location of the dataset	MD_DataIdentification.extent > EX_Extent > EX_GeographicExtent = EX_GeographicBoundingBox or EX_GeographicDescription	Spatial extent information, including the geographic coverage of the dataset defined by a bounding box (westLon, eastLon, southLat, northLat)	Conditional (C)	Yes
Dataset language	MD_DataIdentification.language	Language used for documenting the metadata	Mandatory (M)	Yes
Dataset character set	MD_DataIdentification.characterSet	Character set in which the dataset is encoded	Conditional (C)	Yes
Dataset topic category	MD_DataIdentification.topicCategory	ISO Topic Categories	Mandatory (M)	Yes
Keywords	MD_DataIdentification.Keyword	keywords that identifies a particular subject, object, or topic represented by the dataset according to the GEMET-INSPIRE, OGC RAINBOW, MiraMon Thesaurus, ELTER Vocabularies and Climate and Forecast Standard Names (NVS). Custom keywords are also used to filter metadata records by AD4GD pilot	Optional (O)	Yes
Spatial resolution of the dataset	MD_DataIdentification.spatialResolution > MD_Resolution.equivalentScale or MD_Resolution.distance	Level of detail expressed as a scale factor or a ground sample distance (pixels per meter or geographic scale)	Optional (O)	If possible
Abstract describing the dataset	MD_DataIdentification.abstract	Short description of the dataset, including possible links to examples of application	Mandatory (M)	Yes
Distribution format	MD_Distribution > MD_Format.name and MD_Format.version	Format of the data described	Optional (O)	Yes
Additional extent information for the dataset	MD_DataIdentification.extent > EX_Extent > EX_TemporalExtent or EX_VerticalExtent	Temporal validity or coverage of the dataset	Optional (O)	Yes
Spatial representation type	MD_DataIdentification.spatialRepresentationType	Digital method used to spatially represent geographic information, depending on whether it is vector or grid data	Optional (O)	Yes

ISO19115 element	Domain	Description	Obligation	Present in AD4GD metadata
Reference system	MD_ReferenceSystem	Spatial reference system, defined by geographic coordinates according the EPSG codes	Optional (O)	Yes
Lineage	DQ_DataQuality.lineage > LI_Lineage	Information about the events or source data used in constructing the described data	Optional (O)	If possible
On-line resource	MD_Distribution > MD_DigitalTransferOption.onLine > CI_OnlineResource	URL or location path where is possible to find the dataset (e.g., MinIO, FROST or ODC)	Optional (O)	If possible
Metadata file identifier	MD_Metadata.fileIdentifier	Identifier of the metadata record	Optional (O)	Yes
Metadata standard name	MD_Metadata.metadataStandardName	Name of the standard used to document the metadata	Optional (O)	Yes
Metadata standard version	MD_Metadata.metadataStandardVersion	Version of the metadata standard	Optional (O)	Yes
Metadata language	MD_Metadata.language	Language or languages in which the metadata is provided	Conditional (C)	Yes
Metadata character set	MD_Metadata.characterSet	Character set used to encode the metadata	Conditional (C)	Yes
Metadata point of contact	MD_Metadata.contact > CI_ResponsibleParty	Point of contact for the content of the metadata	Mandatory (M)	Yes
Metadata date stamp	MD_Metadata.dateStamp	Date in which the metadata has been created	Mandatory (M)	Yes

Table 2 ISO 19115 core metadata elements used to document the AD4GD pilot datasets.